

Tender Competition: Business Strategy to Increase Sales (Study Case: PT CSR)

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ABSTRACT: This study examines the business issue that PT Cuindo Sadiya Rizky (PT CSR), a small Indonesian company that provides railway spare parts, is facing, the business relies on a single state-owned company's project tenders, as a result, there are risks like inconsistent revenue, operational delays, and a lack of long-term planning, due to PT CSR's lack of a set system, single primary client, and restricted capacity to fulfill tender requirements, these issues frequently arise, helping PT CSR develop a well-defined and organized B2B business plan is the aim of this study, the backdrop stems from the need for small suppliers in public projects to be more prepared, particularly as market demands and governmental regulations change frequently, the issue in this instance is evidently that there is no increase in the source of income and that no solid foundation for long-term growth has yet been established, the primary presumption is that the business needs a better plan but wishes to continue operating in this tender-based market and by taking more steady, transparent, and expert actions, the study hopes to support PT CSR's survival.

This study employs a thematic qualitative approach using documents, company reviews, and interviews to achieve its objective, the analysis is aided by a number of tools: Porter's Five Forces helps determine how difficult the competition is, the Marketing Mix (4P) is used to evaluate the company's offer to the client, SWOT analysis is used to determine the company's internal strengths and weaknesses, and VRIO determines whether the company has anything unique to offer, several important points emerge from the findings, PT CSR excels at pricing and networks, but struggles with systems and planning, the business must improve its SOPs, diversify its clientele, enhance its tender documents, and form vendor groups in order to participate in larger tenders, all of the recommendations are reasonable and doable within a year, it demonstrates how they can lower risks, stabilize, and continue to expand, the research also adds value to the study of business strategy by showing how theory can be used in real small business cases in developing countries.

KEYWORDS: B2B strategy, marketing strategy, SWOT analysis, TOWS matrix

1. INTRODUCTION

State-Owned Enterprises (BUMN) play a vital role in Indonesia's development through procurement-based projects that are ideally governed by transparent and competitive tender processes, however in practice, limited announcement systems and direct appointments often create high entry barriers, especially for new and smaller firms, PT Cuindo Sadiya Rizky (CSR), a Sukoharjo-based railway spare parts supplier established in 2023, is heavily dependent on such tenders for its revenue, and despite complying with standard procurement procedures beginning from SPPHB receipt to supplier coordination and proposal submission CSR's tender win rate in 2024 stood at only 40%, securing just 4 out of 10 projects, with this serious risk to its financial continuity, given the absence of alternative income streams and the unpredictable nature of the tender ecosystem. The direct appointment method of the BUMN procurement system may limit market competition by obstructing new competitors and reducing the transparency of procurement options, claim Rosisca et al. (2025).

The lack of transparency, combined with ambiguous rejection outcomes and the increasing presence of Chinese-backed multinationals in the sector, further exacerbates CSR's competitive challenges, in this context, formulating a sharper strategic approach is critical to reversing stagnant performance, this study, therefore, seeks to identify the internal and external factors that limit CSR's tender success, evaluate its current market positioning, and propose actionable strategies to improve competitiveness, focusing on 2024 performance data, the research draws from benchmarking insights and stakeholder interviews to offer practical solutions that aim to enhance CSR's bidding effectiveness and ensure sustainable business growth within Indonesia's railway procurement landscape.

2. THEORITICAL FOUNDATION

2.1 Business Strategy

Business strategy is a company's plan to achieve competitive advantage and profitability by choosing how it will compete in its industry, according to Porter (1985) firms can adopt one of three generic strategies which is cost leadership, differentiation, or focus, cost leadership emphasizes efficiency and low-cost operations, differentiation offers unique products or services to justify premium pricing, and focus strategy targets specific market niches with tailored solutions

2.2 Marketing Strategy

A marketing strategy is a functional-area playbook that turns corporate goals into market actions and it decides who the firm will serve, how it will differentiate, and which mix of sales, pricing and communication tools it will deploy, thereby aligning day-to-day marketing work with wider business objectives (Thompson et al., 2020)

2.3 Market Analysis

B2B buying logic is multi-person, data-driven and slow, suppliers therefore start with the STP process:

- Segmentation is a grouping firms on variables such as industry, size or location so that each slice shares similar needs (Kotler & Armstrong, 2014)
- Targeting is an evaluating those slices and selecting the ones the company can serve best, whether via concentrated, differentiated or mass coverage (Khandelwal et al., 2020)
- Positioning is a crafting value proposition that occupies a clear, desirable space in buyers' minds, often visualised with a perceptual map (Kotler et al., 2020).

Execution is channelled through the 4Ps marketing mix which is Product, Price, Place and Promotion augmented in services by People, Process and Physical evidence (Nuseir & Madanat, 2015) Continuous competitor analysis benchmarks rivals on offer, price, branding, reputation and service to spot gaps and defend share (Laakso, 2017)

2.4 Customer Perception of Quality

Customers weigh the gap between expected and experienced performance, in a services they judge reliability, assurance, responsiveness, empathy and tangibles; in products they focus on performance and aesthetics (Restiana, 2020) a well-balanced marketing mix shapes these perceptions and, in turn, loyalty (Nuseir & Madanat, 2015)

2.5 Internal Analysis

- Resource-Based View (RBV) is sustainable advantage stems from unique bundles of tangible and intangible resources plants, patents, people, reputation that rivals cannot easily trade or copy (Madhani, 2010)
- VRIO is a resources must be Valuable, Rare, In-imitable and Organised to deliver lasting rent (Barney, 1991)
- Value Chain is a mapping primary (logistics, operations, marketing, service) and support activities pinpoints cost drivers and differentiation levers inside the firm (Porter, 1985)

2.6 External Analysis

External analysis divided into this three segment, firstly PESTEL scans macro forces political, economic, social, technological, environmental and legal that set the opportunity/threat backdrop (Yusop, 2018), and then Porter's Five Forces gauges industry attractiveness via rivalry, buyer power, supplier power, threat of substitutes and threat of new entrants (Porter, 1979) combining these lenses with direct competitor and customer studies equips managers to pre-empt shocks and exploit trends (Rothaermel, 2016)

2.7 SWOT Analysis

SWOT synthesises internal (Strengths, Weaknesses) and external (Opportunities, Threats) findings into a single grid, helping firms match capabilities to conditions, set priorities and craft coherent strategy (Weng & Liu, 2018)

2.8 Organisational Buying Behaviour

Buying center is organisational purchases are made by a network of initiators, influencers, gatekeepers, deciders and buyers whose varied agendas shape the final choice (Kotler & Keller, 2016), meanwhile buying situations is the needs range from routine straight rebuys to modified rebuys and high-involvement new tasks, each demanding a tailored vendor approach on information, risk reduction and value demonstration (Kotler & Keller, 2016)

2.10 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework illustrates how proposed business strategy is shaped by three main elements which is internal factors, external factors, and the tender bidding approach, internally the VRIO analysis is used to assess whether the firm’s resources and capabilities can provide a sustainable competitive advantage, externally the framework incorporates PESTEL and Porter’s Five Forces to evaluate market conditions and competitive dynamics, the approach integrates customer analysis through STP (Segmentation, Targeting, Positioning)

3. RESEARCH METHOD

3.1 Research Design

This study adopts a qualitative research design that begins with identifying the problem and formulating research questions, it is divided into internal and external assessments, the internal analysis uses the VRIO Framework and Value Chain Analysis to evaluate resources and capabilities, while the external analysis applies PESTEL, Porter’s Five Forces, Competitor Analysis, and STP-based Market Analysis, the findings are synthesized into a SWOT analysis which guides the formulation of strategic recommendations and an implementation plan.

3.2 Data Collection Method

Data collection relies on qualitative techniques, primarily semi-structured interviews, document analysis, and observations. primary data were collected from the CEO of PT CSR and a key client at RAILWAY INDUSTRY SOE, selected through purposive sampling, secondary data such as industry regulations and journal articles, complement the findings with this combination ensures a holistic understanding of internal capabilities and external challenges in tender-based procurement.

Table 1 Data Collection Method

Data	Type	Method
Internal data collection	Primary	Interview, document review, observation
External data collection	Primary & Secondary	Interview, literature review, observation

3.3 Data Analysis Method

This study analyzes data through a qualitative lens, focusing on both internal and external factors, internally VRIO and Value Chain Analysis identify strengths and weaknesses, externally PESTEL, Porter’s Five Forces, and Competitor Analysis assess market dynamics and threats and the STP framework adds a market perspective, with all of these inputs feed into the SWOT analysis, which informs strategic recommendations to enhance PT CSR’s competitiveness in BUMN tenders

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Market Analysis

This section examines PT CSR’s competitive positioning based on market size, customer segmentation, target selection, and positioning within the RAILWAY INDUSTRY SOE tender ecosystem.

4.1.1 Market Size & Market Share

- Total material procurement at RAILWAY INDUSTRY SOE (2024): IDR 1,390,608,000,000 (RKAP 2024)
- PT CSR operating income (2024): IDR 42,623,500 (Financial Report 2024)
- Estimated market share:

$$42,623,500 \div 1,390,608,000,000 \times 100\% = 0.0031\%$$

Although PT CSR has entered the BUMN procurement market, it captures only 0.0031% of RAILWAY INDUSTRY SOE’s material spend highlighting a very small current footprint and substantial room for revenue growth through deeper market penetration

4.1.2 Segmentation, Targeting, Positioning (STP)

4.1.2.1 Segmentation

Based on in-depth interviews with RAILWAY INDUSTRY SOE’s procurement and audit managers (Riana, Yanto, Singgih), customer needs cluster into four segments:

Table 2 Customer Segmentation for PT CSR

Segmentation Type	Parameter	Description
Geographic	Region	Madiun
	Industry	Railway industry
Firmographic	Customer Type	Primary: SOEs Secondary: their subsidiaries
	Tender Size	Small–medium projects (< IDR 3 billion)
Behavioral	Tender Participation	Material-procurement tenders
	Decision Factor	Price competitiveness
Relationship	Customer Relationship	Strong personal relationships with RAILWAY INDUSTRY SOE procurement teams

4.1.2.2 Targeting

Segments are evaluated by growth potential, structural attractiveness, and fit with PT CSR’s capabilities:

Table 3 Target Segment Evaluation

Segment	Growth Potential	Structural Attractiveness	Company Fit
Local Proximity	Driven by TKDN policy and RIPNAS 2030 mandate	Very high	High (CSR’s warehouse in Madiun)
Delivery Flexibility	High urgency & schedule acceleration needs	High	High (agile trading model)
Vendor Experience	Stable repeat-order bias among incumbent vendors	High	Medium (CSR has 4 flawless projects)
Technical Capability	Few qualified domestic Tier-1 suppliers exist	Low–moderate	Low (CSR lacks certifications)

4.1.2.3 Positioning

PT CSR is currently perceived by RAILWAY INDUSTRY SOE as a high-flexibility, low-technical-capability vendor

- High Flexibility
Rapid response to accelerated delivery schedules (like meeting 1-month delivery when contract specified 3 months)
- Low Technical Capability
Lacks certified welding personnel and Mill Certificates required for complex or high-risk projects

This positioning places PT CSR alongside other local trading vendors that excel in responsiveness but have yet to develop formal technical credentials

4.2 Internal Analysis

This section condenses PT CSR’s internal diagnosis into three tools Value Chain, RBV, and VRIO using only the evidence already supplied “S” = strength, “W” = weakness

4.2.1 Value-Chain Snapshot

Table 4 Value Chain Analysis

Link	Current Practice (2024)	SWOT Tag
PRIMARY		
Inbound Logistics	Informal purchasing via CEO’s network; no vendor list/SOP	W
Operations	Pure trading; no SOP / QC, yet 100/100 client score	W
Outbound Logistics	Third-party delivery, no tracking/fleet	W
Marketing & Sales	No sales team/CRM, bids handled solely by CEO	Critical W
Service	No SLA, zero complaints to date	W
SUPPORT		
Firm Infrastructure	3 directors + staff, manual Excel, no audit system	W
HR Management	5 FT + 1 PT, no hiring/training process	W
Technology Development	Static website, WhatsApp/Drive; no ERP/CRM	W
Procurement (internal)	No SOP, assessment, or archives	W

All primary and support activities function informally, sourcing relies on personal contacts, operations lack SOPs, logistics depend on third parties, and marketing is CEO-driven, after-sales service is absent, support functions are also weak, with no HR, IT, or formal procurement system, marketing and sales are critical but fragile due to over-reliance on one individual.

4.2.2 Resource-Based View (RBV)

Table 5 Resources Based View

Category	Key Item	Status	Note
Tangible	Land & buildings (office and warehouse near RAILWAY INDUSTRY SOE)	S	Location suits TKDN/local-vendor bias
	Office equipment (1 printer, phone)	W	Only basic admin support
	Financial capital (debt-free)	W	Cash flow volatile; no reserves
Intangible	Human capital (CEO’s BUMN network)	S	Access to closed tenders
	Reputation (4 projects, 100/100 rating)	S	Trust asset for repeat work
	Strategic partnerships (informal workshops)	W	Personal, undocumented
	Digital assets (website, Drive)	W	Fragmented, non-integrated

Core capability: fast, ad-hoc procurement via personal network—effective for small jobs but non-scalable.

4.2.3 VRIO Summary

Table 6 VRIO Analysis

Resource / Capability	V	R	I	O	Competitive Result
Land & buildings	✓	✓	✗	✗	Temporary Competitive Advantages
Human capital (CEO network)	✓	✓	✓	✗	Temporary Competitive Advantages
Reputation & track record	✓	✓	✓	✓	Sustained Competitive Advantages
Financial capital	✓	✓	✗	✗	Competitive parity / disadvantage
Equipment, digital assets, org structure, partnerships	✗	✗	✗	✗	Competitive disadvantage

PT CSR’s only enduring edge is an impeccable performance record. All other links, resources, and systems remain informal, leaving the firm vulnerable in larger, audited, or technically demanding tenders.

4.3 External Analysis

Below is a compressed, data-based digest of the external forces acting on PT CSR. Each sub-section ends with the direct implication for the firm in SWOT terms.

4.3.1 PESTEL Scan

Table 7 PESTEL Scan

Factor	Salient Evidence (2024 – 2025)	Net Effect on PT CSR	SWOT Tag
Political	SOE-Law No. 1/2025 obliges BUMN to prefer MSME & local vendors but tightens audit & governance rules, political-stability index -0,40 (WB, 2023) rule-of-law still weak (-0.15)	Local-vendor bias helps entry, yet heavier paperwork & transparency expose PT CSR’s informal systems.	Threats
Economic	Transport Ministry budget 2025: IDR 17.7 tn, no new rolling-stock capex, GDP +5.1 % (Q1 2025), TKDN push, metals oversupply may cut input prices.	Steady rail O&M demand and cheaper materials favour a low-capital trader such as PT CSR.	Opportunities
Social	RAILWAY INDUSTRY SOE purposefully awards work to Madiun SMEs, WhatsApp-based coordination matches Javanese relational culture.	Cultural proximity and informal communication remain PT CSR’s soft advantage.	Opportunities
Technological	RAILWAY INDUSTRY SOE runs SAP & e-Proc VMS but final docs still hard-copy, no IoT/barcode required at vendor level.	Low digital barrier lets PT CSR compete without heavy IT investment for now.	Opportunities
Environmental	No green-spec clauses in 4 latest tenders, RAILWAY INDUSTRY SOE’s ESG goals not yet cascaded to vendors.	Absence of sustainability audits buys time; future green rules could surface.	Opportunities (latent Threats)
Legal	Mandatory BPJS & audited FS increasing, ISO 9001/45001 “preferred”, PT CSR lacks audits & certificates.	Compliance gap may block higher-value bids.	Threats

4.3.2 Industry Environment Porter Five Forces

Table 8 Five Forces

Force	Key Drivers	Intensity	SWOT Impact
New Entrants	Easy VMS registration, low start-up capital IDR 30 mn, but invitations hinge on personal trust & cash-flow for pre-payment.	Medium to High	Threats
Supplier Power	Commodities plentiful (bolts, cables) to weak power, custom casting partners hold leverage & demand full pre-pay	Low to Med	Latent Threats
Buyer Power (RAILWAY INDUSTRY SOE)	Strict specs, tiered approval, performance scoring, can split orders or substitute vendors rapidly	High	Threats
Threat of Substitutes	Generic parts easily sourced from bigger players or in-house production if urgent	High	Threats
Competitive Rivalry	Dense field BSR, Atlantic, Latumurni, KSR, evaluation on price, delivery record, documentation	Very High	Threats

Overall industry structure is unfavourable for small, undocumented traders; differentiation must move beyond lowest price.

4.3.3 Customer (RAILWAY INDUSTRY SOE) Behaviour Snapshot

Dimension	Observed Pattern	Implication for PT CSR
Buying Situation	70 % straight rebuy (low-risk small parts); modified rebuy if delivery / quality slips; new-task needs pilot runs.	Keep flawless delivery scores to stay on “straight-rebuy” list; prepare samples & tech clarifications for new-task bids.
Buying-Center Roles	PPC = initiator Engineering = influencer Logistics = gatekeeper & buyer GM/BoD = deciders.	Map contacts accordingly; submit tech docs early to Engineering, keep WhatsApp open for Logistics.
Decision Criteria	1) Quality/non-conformity history 2) Delivery agility 3) Price fit to HPS 4) Local proximity (TKDN)	Maintain 100/100 scorecard; highlight local warehouse; stay within HPS bands

Key opportunity: leverage perfect past scores to lock-in straight-rebuy items while upgrading documentation to move into modified/new-task jobs

4.3.4 Competitor Field

Table 9 Competitor Analysis

Firm	Core Edge	Gap / Vulnerability	Effect on PT CSR
PT BSR	Large volume, Chinese OEM docs, ISO 9001/14001	No local factory to weak TKDN, import lead-time	Threats in high-tech tenders, Opportunities for local-content bids
CV KSR	Madiun location, interior seats know-how	No ISO, tiny scope, single-client reliance	Direct peer, easiest to outpace via better systems (Opportunities)
Atlantic	Modern CNC/laser plant, global quality, export track-record	Premium price; may ignore micro-orders	Threats for high-value jobs, low overlap on small lots
Latumurni	Full ISO-cert steel fabrication, multi-sector scale	Focus on custom heavy builds, less trading agility	Threats in large fabrication, niche Opportunities in small parts

4.3.5 Synthesis External SWOT Keys

Table 10 Synthethos External SWOT Keys

External Factor Block	Net for PT CSR
Political & Legal compliance load rises	Threats because formalise systems, pursue ISO/FS audit.
TKDN & local-vendor push	Opportunities because emphasise Madiun warehouse, local spend.
Digitalisation light-touch (VMS only)	Opportunities because compete without big IT capex, but prepare for future e-contracting.
Price-sensitive, trust-based buyer culture	Opportunities/Threats continue perfect delivery, build documented track record.
Competitive crowding by certified fabricators	Threats because shield core micro-spares niche; partner for big bids.

Focus on compliance upgrades (ISO 9001 and audited FS) and a local-content positioning narrative to convert the many Opportunities above into real bid wins while neutralising the two structural threats (governance & rivalry).

4.3 SWOT Analysis

Table 11 SWOT Analysis

Table IV.13 SWOT Analysis PT Cuindo Sadiya Rizky (CSR)

Strengths (S)	Weaknesses (W)
<p>S1 Specializes in small railway components</p> <p>S2 Strategic location near RAILWAY INDUSTRY SOE</p> <p>S3 Pricing flexibility and negotiation agility</p> <p>S4 In-depth knowledge of RAILWAY INDUSTRY SOE's procurement procedures</p> <p>S5 Informal rapport with key RAILWAY INDUSTRY SOE personnel</p> <p>S6 Adaptable supply chain for custom project needs</p> <p>S7 Efficient local supplier network supports fast procurement</p> <p>S8 High responsiveness to sudden tender demands</p>	<p>W1 No formally documented SOPs</p> <p>W2 Administrative and technical errors in tender documents</p> <p>W3 Limited technical capabilities; unable to handle complex projects</p> <p>W4 No permanent project teams due to short-term organizational structure</p> <p>W5 No budget for certification, training, or quality upgrades</p> <p>W6 Weak financial documentation and risk evaluation systems</p> <p>W7 Over-reliance on CEO's informal networks</p>
Opportunities (O)	Threats (T)
<p>O1 TKDN policy promotes use of local components</p> <p>O2 Growing SOE revitalization and procurement programs</p> <p>O3 Potential for multi-year SOE contracts</p> <p>O4 E-procurement digitalization offers wider tender visibility</p> <p>O5 SOEs seeking more efficient, low-cost vendors</p> <p>O6 Opportunity to join consortia for large-value tenders</p> <p>O7 Potential regional vendor alliance to boost competitiveness</p>	<p>T1 Sole dependency on RAILWAY INDUSTRY SOE as main client</p> <p>T2 Intense competition from low-cost Chinese suppliers</p> <p>T3 Lack of transparency in RAILWAY INDUSTRY SOE's four tender categories</p> <p>T4 Sudden changes in tax and procurement regulations</p> <p>T5 Absence of feedback hampers strategy refinement</p> <p>T6 New certifications and audit rules burden small vendors</p> <p>T7 Risk of product substitution due to generic product nature</p> <p>T8 Weak competitiveness in technical tenders vs. certified rivals</p> <p>T9 Multisector competitors with production facilities dominate large projects</p> <p>T10 Advanced competitors benefit from stronger documentation/import capacity</p> <p>T11 Unmet admin prerequisites (audits, BPJS).</p> <p>T12 Low-entry competitors with formal structures emerge</p> <p>T13 Competitive pressure from RAILWAY INDUSTRY SOE's informal, fast-paced evaluation norms</p>

PT CSR's core strengths lie in its flawless delivery record, strong CEO network, strategic Madiun location, and cost-efficient operations, however it faces internal weaknesses such as the absence of SOPs, weak documentation, limited technical depth, unstable cash flow, and over-reliance on the CEO, and externally the company can seize opportunities from TKDN policies, steady rail maintenance demand, growing e-procurement visibility, consortia bids, and price-sensitive SOEs, yet it must also confront threats including rising compliance requirements, certified competitors, opaque evaluation processes, client dependency, and high product substitutability.

4.5 Proposed Solution

4.5.1 TOWS Matrix

Table 12 TOWS Matrix Strategic Options for PT Cuindo Sadiya Rizky (CSR)

S–O Strategy (Maximize)	S–T Strategy (Defend)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SO1 Join new BUMN tenders using proven track record SO2 Leverage Madiun location for local content advantage SO3 Promote flexible, low-cost procurement model to budget-tight SOEs SO4 Emphasize fast logistics response for urgent government projects SO5 Form joint bids for large-value packages with regional players SO6 Partner with local SMEs to meet TKDN targets SO7 Pitch quick-quote agility for cost-sensitive tender wins 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ST1 Monitor procurement rules via informal BUMN links ST2 Offer lowest price early to avoid late-stage price wars ST3 Formalize insights to navigate unclear evaluation systems ST4 Bundle offers (goods + services) to reduce substitution risk ST5 Respond quickly to informal tender inquiries ST6 Leverage agility to outperform rigid competitors ST7 Use warehouse proximity to beat imported alternatives
W–O Strategy (Improve)	W–T Strategy (Mitigate)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WO1 Develop SOPs in line with SOE e-procurement platforms WO2 Simplify tender documentation to align with SOE efficiency needs WO3 Upskill staff on TKDN basics to meet compliance needs WO4 Build semi-permanent teams to handle recurring tender types WO5 Allocate funds for multi-year framework contracts WO6 Create clear financial dashboards to attract strategic partners WO7 Actively track open tenders outside of known contacts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WT1 Address lack of SOPs to reduce risks in opaque bidding WT2 Create feedback loop to improve future bid performance WT3 Train for ISO/other certification access despite current limitations WT4 Improve audit and BPJS reporting to boost compliance credibility WT5 Reduce cash flow risks and client over-dependence WT6 Expand networking beyond CEO-only ties to build long-term trust

To maximize strengths (SO), PT CSR should leverage its performance score and local presence to win new tenders, offer quick and affordable delivery, and form joint bids for larger packages, to defend against threats (ST), it should monitor regulation updates, price competitively from the outset, offer bundled solutions, and use its warehouse to reduce delivery times, to improve weaknesses (WO), CSR must develop e-procurement-ready SOPs, train staff on TKDN and build scalable financial tools, to mitigate threats (WT), it needs to fill structural gaps, prepare for certification, improve reporting, diversify its client base, and expand beyond the CEO’s network

4.6 Implementation Plan

Table 13 Implementation Plan

No	Programme (what)	Linked Codes	Target Window	Success Metric	Owner
1	Issue tender SOP & flowchart	WO-1, WT-1	Month 1-Month 2	SOP used in all new bids	Ops Dir
2	Build finance dashboard & cash-plan	WO-6, WT-5	Month 1-Month 3	Live dashboard, monthly updates	Finance Dir

3	Recruit admin & technical staff	WT-5, WT-3	Month1 - Month3	2 staff on-board	CEO
4	One-click tender doc templates	WO-2, WT-2	Month 3 - Month 4	Template applied in 3 bids	Tender Admin
5	Register in new rail BUMN e-procs	SO-1, WO-7	Month 3 – Month 4	Vendor ID in 1 new SOE	CEO
6	Basic TKDN/QA training (2 staff)	WO-3, WT-3	Month 3 - Month 5	Certificates obtained	Ops Dir
7	Form semi-permanent bid team	WO-4	Month 4	Team used in 2 tenders	Ops Dir
8	Sign consortium MoU with vendor	SO-5, SO-6	Month 5 - Month 7	1 joint bid submitted	CEO
9	Activate real-time tender alerts	ST-5, SO-4	Month 6	Notification tool live	Tender Admin
10	Enrol on 2 additional LPSE platforms	SO-4, WO-1	Month 6 – Month 8	Active profiles = ≥ 3	Admin Staff
11	Develop bundled-offer proposal kit	ST-4, SO-3	Month 7 - Month 8	Bundle used in ≥ 1 bid	Tender Team
12	Post-bid review & lessons-learned loop	WT-2	Start Month 9 and still ongoing	Review doc after each loss	Tender Team
13	Complete BPJS enrolment & 1st audit	WT-4	Month 10-Month 12	Audit report & BPJS card	CEO / Finance

In months 1–3, PT CSR will publish SOPs, launch a financial dashboard, and hire two staff members, in months 3–5, it will register on new e-proc platforms, train staff, and prepare tender templates, in months 5–8, it plans to sign a consortium MoU, enable real-time tender alerts, and develop bundled service offerings, in months 9–12, it will conduct post-bid evaluations, complete its first audit, and ensure BPJS compliance, the success metrics include SOP adoption, two new SOE vendor registrations, use of new templates in three bids, and at least one joint submission.

5. CONCLUSION

This study investigates PT Cuindo Sadiya Rizky’s (PT CSR) challenges in winning BUMN tenders by addressing three key questions related to market characteristics, marketing strategy, and implementation plans, the first analysis reveals that PT CSR operates in a highly competitive railway spare parts market dominated by RAILWAY INDUSTRY SOE as the sole major buyer, with intense price competition, opaque procurement systems, and pressure to maintain administrative and technical efficiency, to address the second question, internal analysis using VRIO and Value Chain combined with an STP-based marketing approach shows that while PT CSR benefits from flexible pricing and informal vendor networks, it lacks documented processes and strategic segmentation, as a result, the most suitable strategy is a focus differentiation strategy that emphasizes delivery accuracy and customization, coupled with cost leadership to maintain price competitiveness, finally to answer the third question, a one-year TOWS-based implementation plan is proposed highlighting key steps such as forming a semi-permanent project team, formalizing SOPs, mapping new BUMN clients, digitizing document systems, and forming vendor consortia all aimed at reducing client dependency and enhancing PT CSR’s tender competitiveness.

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